

EFFECT OF CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES ON ACADEMIC SUCCESS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract

In this research article, the researcher has presented an explanation of the relationship between participation in curricular activities and academic success by comprehensively reviewing various recent literatures. The researcher concluded that participation in curricular activities has both positive and negative impact on the academic performance of students of all categories. Sports being a large part of the curricular spectrum, this article also attempts to examine studies that analyze the effects of physical and mental activity on academic performance. Previous studies reviewed in the relevant literature show that curricular activities have a positive impact on academics and students when they contribute to a balanced life, self-confidence, an increased sense of personal responsibility, and feelings of belonging and contribution to school. These curricular activities have a negative impact when they create an overloaded individual schedule and require students to define themselves primarily based on their activities other than that of other students. Related studies also found that the general effects of physical and mental activity had both positive and negative correlations with academic success, but most studies lacked the evidence needed to draw any definitive conclusions regarding the relationship. Thus, curricular activities have become an integral part of the modern-day educational curriculum. It provides an opportunity for positive character building to the students. The main objective of the present study is to identify the impact of curricular activities on the academic performance of students.

Introduction:

India is the largest democracy in the world. Democracies as we know are nourished by democratic methods adopted in various institutions of a country. It depends more on the quality of its schools than on the educational contribution of any other single social institution with the possible exceptions of the home. The quality of school will depend upon the educational experiences necessary for the students in the modern Indian schools. A great variety of educational experiences is to be provided in the school programme which may contribute to a long, happy, and normal life. Only well-adjusted citizens will be able to ensure national development in all its

parameters. Co-curricular activities sponsored or recognized by a school which are not part of the academic curriculum but are considered an essential part of the life of an educational institution (Othoo & Omondi, 2022). In order to develop the child's body and mind demand proper nurturing of its physical and intellectual qualities as a few of the major determinants of his personality. Therefore, modern educational methods emphasize the overall development of the students. The educational process is not a static concept or onetime procedure, rather it is a continuous and long-term process that is diversified as curricular or academic activities or curricular and non-academic activities. Curricular activities are those that are not directly related to the prescribed curriculum. It includes drama, debates, sports, fine arts, literary activities, gaming activities, that helps in holistic development of the students. Nowadays, colleges organize cultural fests, talent hunts, college fests to keep the students engaged and learn to get exposure to public and management activities. This study is an initial attempt to understand perspectives of students to understand whether they support the fact that co-curricular activities are equally important for assessing student's overall performance. Evaluation of university students only on the basis of written exams doesn't always becomes reliable. The study also tries to understand whether students support the idea of modification in the pattern of exam. The study can be helpful to decision makers of educational institutions and make their decision in assessing today's students and developing them.

Previously the purpose of education was confined to the teaching of subjects in the curriculum. The social activities were regarded as 'extras'. A weak student had no right to go to the playgrounds or to cultural functions. Gradually this attitude of hostility changed into that of indifference. These activities were not supervised nor was any guidance given. But now the concept of education has changed. All round development of the child is the theme of new education. When the child comes to school he becomes mentally, physically, spiritually, socially, and vocationally well developed and get mastery in all aspects of growth and development through the educational process. Now it is recognized that these activities are valuable media for developing proper attitudes, habits, interests, ideals among pupils. Because of their importance in education, they have been renamed as "curricular activities", as they form an integral part of the school curriculum. Their organization therefore needs much care and forethought. The Mudaliar Education Commission 1952-53 remarks "The School is not merely a place of formal learning whose main concern is to communicate a certain prescribed quantum of knowledge but rather as a living and organic community which is primarily interested in training its pupils in what we have

called the gracious art of living. I knowledge and learning are undoubtedly of value, but they must be acquired as a bi-product or interested activity because it is only then that they can become a vital part of the student's mind and personality and influence his behavior. But the 'Art of Living' is a much more comprehensive concept than the acquisition of knowledge, however intelligently planned. It includes training in the habits and graces of social life and capacity for co-operative group work: it calls for patience, good temper, sincerity, fellow-feeling, and discipline. These can only be cultivated in the context of social life and the many curricular activities that must find a recognized place in every school."

These educational experiences comprise experiences inside as well as outside the classroom, curricular as well as extra-curricular, curricular as well as co-curricular to cover all facts of growth pattern mentioned above and ensure balance development of the ' child and good citizenship for the country. So, curricular activities are now considered to be the intrinsic part of the educational Endeavour in a school. Lately these were called extra-curricular activities. But now these have been recognized as a part of regular curriculum for the complete education of the child, and hence these are now curricular. In fact, curricular activities and academic activities are now considered complementary to each other, both deserving equal weight and emphasis in the total programme of the school.

Effects of Curricular Activities on student's achievements

Curricular activities have immense importance for the overall development or holistic development of each student because it brings holistic and sustainable growth in their life. Study reveals that co-curricular activities install moral values among students, leadership quality, teamwork and also prepares them for goals and challenges in their life. Curricular activities are an essential part of a student's life and help in enhancing the learning process of students at colleges. These activities are meant to bring social skills, intellectual skills, moral values, personality progress and character appeal in students. The respondents who actively participated in games registered improvements in their academic performed based on their entry behaviours. This agrees with numerous studies that have shown a positive relationship between co-curricular activities and academic performance (**Broh, 2002; Poh-Sun Seow and Gary, 2014**). Curricular activity participation is associated with an improved grade point average, higher educational aspirations, increased college attendance, and reduced absenteeism (**Burrows and McCormack, 2011**).

Curricular activities have been found to have a positive impact on students' academic achievements. While academic performance primarily relies on classroom learning, curricular activities complement and enhance the overall educational experience. Here are some of the effects of curricular activities on students' academic achievements (**Tanner, 2017**):

Promoting self-confidence: Burrows and McCormack (2011) also suggested that extracurricular activities provide a way to build self-confidence, which can have a positive effect on academic performance. By achieving personal goals, receiving recognition for accomplishments, and regularly interacting with others in an intricate social system, students were better able to feel productive and self-efficacious.

Increasing sense of contribution and duty: previous literature supports this claim, reporting that this sense of duty often seems to carry over into the academic realm, resulting in lower drop-out rates and higher academic achievement (**Cosden et al., 2004; Mahoney & Cairns, 1997**).

Cultivating feelings of belongingness: Consistent with the previously mentioned ideas, one could also reasonably hypothesize that the more a student feels that he or she belongs at school, the more likely that student will perform well academically. Moreover, considering that extracurricular activities provide a social atmosphere where students are encouraged to achieve in the name of the school, it is reasonable to conclude that extracurricular involvement might provide an ideal setting to feel that belonging.

Improved Time Management: Engaging in co-curricular activities requires students to effectively manage their time between academic responsibilities and extracurricular commitments. This skill is transferable to their academic pursuits, helping them prioritize tasks, meet deadlines, and achieve better time management overall.

Enhanced Cognitive Skills: Many co-curricular activities, such as debate clubs, math competitions, or science fairs, foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills. These skills directly contribute to academic success, as students develop the ability to approach academic tasks with a more logical and structured mindset.

Strengthened Motivation and Engagement: Co-curricular activities provide an avenue for students to explore their interests, passions, and talents outside of the traditional academic setting. Participating in activities they enjoy can boost their motivation and engagement levels, which can positively impact their overall attitude towards learning and academic performance.

Improved Social Skills: Co-curricular activities often involve teamwork, collaboration, and interaction with peers and mentors. Students develop social skills such as effective communication, empathy, leadership, and cooperation, which can positively impact their academic performance. Strong social skills can lead to better classroom participation, group projects, and a supportive learning environment.

Balanced Development: Engaging in co-curricular activities helps students achieve a balanced development by fostering their physical, emotional, and social well-being. When students feel well-rounded and fulfilled in various aspects of their lives, it can positively impact their academic achievements. A balanced life could be characterized as a way of life in which a healthy balance between work, leisure, and other personal pursuits is maintained. For developing adolescents, life balance and leisure activities are positive predictors of academic achievement and may help students maintain an optimal level of efficiency (**Bergin, 1992**).

Stress Reduction: Co-curricular activities provide a break from the academic routine and can serve as a stress-relieving outlet. Participating in activities like sports, music, or art can help reduce stress levels, promote mental well-being, and enhance students' ability to concentrate and perform better academically.

Expanded Learning Opportunities: Co-curricular activities often expose students to diverse experiences and knowledge outside of their academic curriculum. This exposure broadens their horizons, encourages interdisciplinary thinking, and fosters a love for lifelong learning, which can have a positive impact on their academic achievements.

It's important to note that while curricular activities can contribute positively to academic achievements, it's crucial to strike a balance between academics and extracurricular commitments. Students should prioritize their academic responsibilities and ensure they have enough time and energy to devote to their studies.

Conclusion

Curricular activities, also known as extracurricular activities or co-curricular activities, can have a positive impact on the academic achievements of students. While academic success is primarily measured by grades and test scores, curricular activities offer a range of benefits that can contribute to overall academic performance. Participating in curricular activities requires students to balance their academic responsibilities with other commitments. This helps develop time management skills, as students learn to prioritize their tasks, meet deadlines, and allocate time efficiently. These

skills can have a direct positive impact on academic performance. Curricular activities often involve planning and organizing events, projects, or teams. By taking part in such activities, students develop organizational skills, including setting goals, creating action plans, and coordinating resources. These skills can transfer to their academic work, allowing them to stay organized, meet project requirements, and complete assignments effectively. Engaging in curricular activities that align with students' interests can boost their motivation and enthusiasm for learning. When students are passionate about a particular activity, they often find it easier to channel that enthusiasm into their academic studies as well. Curricular activities provide a sense of purpose, which can translate into improved academic focus and dedication. Many curricular activities involve teamwork, collaboration, and communication. Through these activities, students learn how to work effectively with their peers, resolve conflicts, and express their ideas clearly. Strong social skills can positively impact academic performance, as they facilitate group projects, class discussions, and interactions with teachers.

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